

IPBES Values Chapter 2 - Literature review regarding values, valuation and decision-making / IPBES values assessment (2.8)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. Identifying “the way in which different worldviews, associated with different types of values have been included in decision-making contexts” is part of chapter 2’s mandate according to the IPBES scoping document for the values assessment. Subsection 2.4.2.3’s objective is to provide evidence on this topic. Expert knowledge and searches, using general concepts and key concepts, were utilised to gather information for this purpose. This literature review is part of the stage 2 strategy that chapter 2 incorporated to bring different sources of evidence appropriate for each section and subsection.

Process overview

Protocol

The evidence to inform section 2.4.2.3 was gathered through three processes.

Process 1: References based on expert knowledge

Based on 30 years of research experience in the field of environmental governance, the leader of this literature review selected an extensive number of publications (journal articles and books) to structure subsection 2.4.2.

Process 2: Searches using search strings with general concepts

To complement the references based on expert knowledge, four searches were done using different combinations of broad concepts related to institutions, decision-making and values. The purpose of these searches was to fill in any gaps in the literature selected in the first process.

The search engine used for all searches was Google Scholar, since that engine provides results of both academic papers and books. All searches were carried out in English.

Searches were done in steps. First, the terms were searched for 'wherever in the document', which then led to filtering the results whenever the project leader found it necessary. The filters were done by restricting the search terms only in the title or headline, and then, in the date (2010 and after). The details of each of the searches (and corresponding filters) are described **(A)** and only search terms and final samples (of relevant publications used to inform section 2.4.2.3 and annex 2.15) are presented below. Note that two searches are presented together as results of the samples extracted overlapped.

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TS 1 =
("institutions" AND "decision-making") AND NOT ("education" OR "educational" OR "learning")
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 7 relevant publications

Details search 2 & search 3:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TS 2=
("institutions" AND "environment" AND "environmental" AND "decision-making") AND NOT ("education" OR "educational" OR "learning")
TS 3=
"institutions" AND "environment" AND "environmental" AND "decision-making" AND "A review") AND NOT ("education" OR "educational" OR "learning" OR "academic")
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 17 relevant publications

Details search 4:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TS 4=
("values" AND "environment" AND "environmental" AND "decision-making")
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 7 relevant publications (+ 1 book)

Treatment applied: The 31 relevant publications (+ 1 book) obtained from searches 1-4 were fully read and the evidence was used along with references from Process 1 to develop the text for section 2.4.2.3.

Process 3: Searches using search strings based on more specific words or concepts

While writing the text it was noted that further evidence was needed to inform specific topics. Hence, searches 5-16 were carried out.

Searches were done following the same steps as described for process 2. Full details of each of the searches (and corresponding filters) can be found in **(A)**. Only search terms and final samples (of relevant publications used to inform section 2.4.2.3 and annex 2.15) are presented below. Note that nine searches are presented together as results of the samples extracted overlapped.

Details searches 5 & 6:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TS 5=
▪ ("modern agriculture" AND "environmental impacts")
TS 6=
▪ ("modern agriculture" AND "pollution")
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 10 relevant publications

Details searches 7, 8 & 9:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TS 7=
▪ ("corporate" AND "decision-making")
TS 8=
▪ ("corporate social responsibility" AND "decision-making")
TS 9=
▪ TITLE ("corporate social responsibility")
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 33 relevant publications

Details search 10:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

TS 10=
("poverty" AND "deforestation")

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 10 relevant publications

Details search 11:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

TS 11=
("greenwashing")

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 23 relevant publications

Details search 12:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

TS 12=
(values public policy)

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 18 relevant publications (+1 book)

Details searches 13 & 14:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

TS 13=
("extractivist policies")

TS 14=
("extractivism, state, business")

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 27 relevant publications

Details searches 15 & 16:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

TS 15=
("economic growth as dominating goal")

TS 14=
("economic growth paradigm")

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 11 relevant publications

Treatment applied: The 132 relevant publications (+ 1 book) obtained from searches 5-16 were fully read and the evidence was used along with references from Process 1 and Process 2 to complete the information for section 2.4.2.3.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.8_8-2020_(A)	PDF	186 KB	Full report, as described by the leader of this review, of the processes followed and the searches performed